

SMALL RUMINANT PRODUCTION CHARACTERISTICS BY RURAL FARM-FAMILIES IN NAERLS-ADOPTED AND NON-ADOPTED VILLAGES IN NORTH-WESTERN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Small ruminant farmers in National Agricultural Extension and Research Liaison Services (NAERLS) adopted and Non-adopted villages in North-Western zone of Nigeria were the focus of this study. One hundred and forty respondents (35 from each of the four villages) were randomly selected from two each of NAERLS-adopted villages (NAV, Sakadadi and Tundu Iya) and Non-adopted villages (NADV, Bomo and Salanke). Primary data were collected using interview scheduled. Secondary data were also utilized for the study. Data collected on socio-economic characteristics of the respondents were analyzed using frequencies counts and percentages. Chi-squares was used to test the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between the production characteristics in the NAERLS-adopted and non-adopted villages in the study area. Result showed that most of the respondents were male in the village groups (84.3% in NAV and 71.4% in NDAV). The respondents in NAV (69.9%) and NADV (78.5%) were mainly in their active age of between 20 to 50 years old and most are married (88.6% and 72.9% for NAV and NDAV, respectively). Size of small ruminant flock, type of products usually obtained and the type of market in which life animals are sold are all similar ($P>0.05$) in the two village groups. The labour required in small ruminant production is mostly supplied by children and women in NAV (77.14%) and 60% in NDAV. Improved practices like hay and silage making, selection for breeding, use of raised platform to prevent cold and provision of medications were used more by respondents in NAV (52.9%) than those from NDAV (22.9%). Membership of farmers' association indicated a significant non-similar response ($P<0.05$) between the NAV (97.1%) and NADV (17.1%). There is a marked difference ($P<0.01$) in farmers' access to extension services; indicating that more farmers in NAV (91.4%) had access to extension services than farmers in NADV (28.6%). The above findings clearly show that the mode of small ruminant production is not similar in NAERLS-adopted and Non-adopted villages. It is therefore recommended that the adopted village concept should be well funded and the number of the villages increased. Also, special attention should be paid to livestock especially small ruminants.

KEYWORDS: NAERLS, Adopted villages, small ruminants

INTRODUCTION

Small ruminant animals (sheep and goats) play a significant role in the food chain and overall livelihoods of rural households where they are largely the property of women and their children (Lebbie, 2004). The basic production characteristics of small ruminant include the flock management system, size of the flock, feeding regime, labour use, litter productivity, health management, source of finance and market availability. Small ruminant are an important but neglected resource in developing countries (El-Aich and Waterhouse, 1999). Government policies are mainly geared to crop and cattle production (Dubeuf *et al.*, 2004; Devendra, 2002). Lack of information on the contribution of small ruminant to rural households is assumed to be one principal reason for the non-recognition of their importance by policy makers and relevant institutions. Lapar *et al.* (2003) stated that smallholders generally have inadequate capital resources (physical, financial resources and intellectual capital resources such as experience, education and extension).

Households in rural areas do not usually have access to banking facilities and thus have come to rely on investment in their small ruminant stock, serving as "backyard savings of money" (Lebbie, 2004). The adopted village concept was introduced in 1996 under the World Bank assisted programme to address inaccessibility of improved technologies generated by research and provide an effective linkage among research, extension and farmers

(Abubakar, 2008 and Oyedokun, 2009). There is a need for good understanding of small ruminant production characteristics of the rural farm families if effective intervention is to be achieved. This paper is therefore aimed at examining, for the purpose of comparison of, small ruminant production characteristics by rural farm-families in NAERLS-adopted and Non-adopted villages in the North-western Nigeria. Specifically, it will assess the socio-economic characteristics of the small ruminant owners, identify their production characteristics and suggest possible ways of improvement.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Small ruminant farmers in National Agricultural Extension and Research Liaison Services (NAERLS) adopted and Non-adopted villages (NADV) in North-Western zone of Nigeria were the focus of this study. NAERLS has 12 adopted villages in all, 5 thematic i.e. programme-based, 1 in each of the 5 agro-ecological zones and 2 adopted by the headquarters. Table 1 contains the details of NAERLS-adopted villages (NAV). One hundred and forty respondents (35 from each of the four villages) were randomly selected from two each of NAV (Sakadadi and Tundu Iya) and Non-adopted villages (Bomo and Salanke). Bomo and Salanke are in Giwa Local Government of Kaduna State, Sakadadi is in Sabon-Gari Local Government Area of Kaduna State while Tundu Iya is in Funtua Local Government of Katsina State. Primary data were collected using interview scheduled which had been pre-tested and subjected to face validity. Secondary data were also utilized for this study. Data collected on socio-economic characteristics of the respondents were analyzed using frequencies counts and percentages (SPSS, 2008). Chi-squares was used to test the hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between the production characteristics in the NAERLS-adopted and non-adopted villages in the study area.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Socio-economic characteristics of small ruminant owners in NAERLS-adopted villages (NAV) and Non-adopted villages (NDAV) is shown in Table 2. Most of the respondents were male in the village groups (84.3% in NAV and 71.4% in NDAV). This disagrees with some findings that women constitute the majority of agricultural force in Nigeria (Pala, 1980 and Idachaba, 1980). It however agrees with the findings of Abu and Agun (1970) that reported low participation of female in farming occupation in Nigeria. According to Pala (1980) and Ogunwale *et al.* (2006), agricultural operations dominated by women in different countries of Africa include livestock husbandry among others. However, the extent of domination of any of these operations by women varies from culture to culture. The respondents in NAV (69.9%) and NADV (78.5%) were mainly in their active age of between 20 to 50 years old and most are married (88.6% and 72.9% for NAV and NDAV, respectively). The fact that agriculture (especially livestock production) is still carried out by able-bodied people is buttressed in this study. Educationally, 67.1% and 48.5% of NAV and NDAV had only primary or no formal education, respectively. In both village groups, the farmers interviewed were mostly artisans or farmers (88.6% for NAV and 74.3% for NDAV). The respondents in NAV were more polygamous (82.8%) than those in NDAV (67.1%). The proportion of respondents with more than four children was higher in NAV (88.6%) than in NDAV (68.6%).

Table 3 a and b show the result of Chi-squares test of hypothesis. Size of small ruminant flock, type of products usually obtained and the type of market in which live animals are sold are all similar ($P > 0.05$) in the two village groups. The people in the NAV reared more of sheep (54.3%) than goats while goats were more prominent (45.7%) in the NDAV than sheep (18.6%). The number of respondents who supplement grazing is higher in NAV (91.4%) than in NDAV (74.3%). The labour required in small ruminant production is mostly supplied by children and women in NAV (77.14%) and 60% in NDAV. This is contrary to the findings of Budisatria (2000) that small ruminants were the responsibility of the parents, while children were not much involved in small ruminant activities. However, the availability of household labour is critical to small ruminant production because rural farm-families cannot rely on hired labour to manage their small ruminants.

Twice-yearly parturition was more prominent in NAV (64.3%) than in NDAV (32.9%) also, multiple births occurred more in NAV (82.9%) than in NDAV (61.4%). Improved practices like hay and silage making, selection for breeding, use of raised platform to prevent cold and provision of medications were used more by respondents in NAV (52.9%) than those from NDAV (22.9%). Most of the respondents in the two village groups fund their small ruminant production through their personal income. This finding suggest low productivity, however, improvement

in production can make a significant contribution to improved human welfare, rural sector growth and in reducing poverty (Devendra and Chantalakhana, 2002, Kosgey *et al.*, 2006).

Membership of farmers' association indicated a significant non-similar response ($P < 0.05$) between the NAV (97.1%) and NADV (17.1%). This implies that the mobilization of farmers into various organizations has been effective in the adopted villages. This might have had a positive impact on the adoption of innovations/technologies in the adopted villages. Kosgey *et al.* (2006) argued that formation of farmers associations and development of marketing facilities would help and enable farmers to get better prices for their animals and/or products. Meanwhile, the high farmers involvement in cooperative activities in NAV cannot be divorced from the presence of NAERLS extension activities. This corroborates the findings of Issa (2008) that extension agents have high competence in formation and organization of farmers' groups. There is a marked difference ($P < 0.01$) in farmers' access to extension services; indicating that more farmers in NAV (91.4%) had access to extension services than farmers in NADV (28.6%). This result was expected since adopted villages are expected to enjoy more frequent visits at least by the adopting NARIs. All the respondents in NAV and 81.4% in NADV indicated that small ruminant rearing is a profitable venture. This is a highly positive perception that small ruminant production is profitable. The extension implication of these findings is that farmers will be willing to adopt technologies that will help them to improve their production.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The above findings clearly show that the mode of small ruminant production is not similar in NAERLS-adopted and Non-adopted villages. Significant and dis-similarity were found in the feeding of the animals; labour use; membership of farmers associations; access to extension and farmers' perception of small ruminant profitability. This further indicates that it is worthwhile to invest in the adopted villages through the National Agricultural Research Institutes (NARIs).

It is therefore recommended that the adopted village concept should be well funded and the number of the villages increased. Also, special attention should be paid to livestock especially small ruminants. This will ensure reduction in the level of food insecurity in the country.

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Table 1: Distributions of NAERLS adopted villages

S/N	Adopted village	Local Government	State	Zone
1.	Nasarawan Buhari	Sabon Gari	Kaduna	Headquarters
2.	Sakadadi	Giwa	Kaduna	Headquarters
3.	Tudun Iya	Funtua	Katsina	North West
4.	Nwogi	Katcha	Niger	North Central
5.	Shurari	Lere	Borno	North East
6.	Amoji Ladu Imenyi	Bende	Umudike	South East
7.	Akufo	Ido	Oyo	South West

Table 2: Social distributions of small ruminant owners in adopted and non-adopted villages

Variable	Groupings	Adopted villages (NAV)	Non-adopted villages (NADV)
Sex of respondents	Male	59 (84.3)	50 (71.4)
	Female	11 (15.7)	20 (28.6)
Age of respondents	20-30	8 (11.4)	11 (15.7)
	31-40	29 (41.4)	26 (37.1)
	41-50	12 (17.1)	18 (25.7)
	51-60	19 (27.1)	9 (12.9)
	61 and above	2 (2.9)	6 (8.6)
Marital status	Single	3 (4.3)	11 (15.7)
	Married	62 (88.6)	51 (72.9)
	Divorced	5 (7.1)	7 (10.0)
	Widowed	0 (0.0)	1 (0.7)
Education status	Non	26 (37.1)	22 (31.4)
	Primary	21 (30.0)	12 (17.1)
	Secondary	18 (25.7)	29 (41.1)
	Tertiary	5 (7.1)	7 (10.0)
Occupation	Artisans	18 (25.7)	23 (32.9)
	Farmers	44 (62.9)	29 (41.4)
	Civil servants	3 (4.3)	11 (15.7)
	Housewife	4 (5.7)	5 (7.1)
	Unemployed	1 (1.4)	2 (2.9)
Type of family	Monogamy	9 (12.9)	16 (22.9)
	Polygamy	58 (82.8)	47 (67.1)
	Non	3 (4.3)	7 (10.0)
Number of children	Non	2 (2.9)	8 (11.4)
	1-4	6 (8.6)	14 (20.0)
	5-7	22 (31.4)	20 (28.6)
	8-10	20 (28.6)	19 (27.1)
	11 and above	20 (28.6)	9 (12.9)

Table 3a: Chi-squares test of small ruminant production characteristics in NAERLS-adopted and Non-adopted villages

Variables	Groupings	Adopted villages* (NAV)	Non-adopted villages* (NADV)	Chi-squares	Degree of freedom	Probability level	Decision
Types of small ruminant kept	Sheep only	2 (2.9)	32 (45.7)	39.180	2	0.000	Significant (P<0.01)
	Goats only	38 (54.3)	13 (18.6)				
	Sheep and goats	30 (42.9)	25 (35.7)				
Flock management system	Intensive	8 (11.4)	5 (7.1)	11.344	2	0.01	Significant (P<0.01)
	Semi-intensive	59 (84.3)	49 (70.0)				
	Extensive	3 (4.3)	16 (22.9)				
Size of small ruminant flock	1-3	15 (21.4)	7 (10.0)	4.130	4	0.389	Not significant (P>0.05)
	4-6	17 (24.3)	24 (34.3)				
	7-9	19 (27.1)	20 (28.6)				
	10-12	12 (17.1)	12 (17.1)				
	13 and above	7 (10.0)	7 (10.0)				
Feeding of the animal	Household waste	4 (5.7)	10 (14.3)	7.413	2	0.025	Significant (P<0.05)
	Grazing	2 (2.9)	8 (11.4)				
	Combination of all	64 (91.4)	52 (74.3)				
Labour use	Children and women	54 (77.14)	42 (60.0)	17.737	2	0.001	Significant (P<0.01)
	Men	10 (14.3)	22 (31.4)				
	Any person in the household	6 (8.6)	6 (8.6)				
Frequency of reproduction per year	Once	21 (30.0)	34 (48.6)	14.955	0.001	0.001	Significant (P<0.01)
	Twice	45 (64.3)	23 (32.9)				
	I don't know	4 (5.7)	13 (18.6)				
Average number of offspring produce at a time	One	12 (17.1)	27 (38.6)	10.043	3	0.018	Significant (P<0.05)
	Two	53 (75.7)	42 (60.0)				
	Three	3 (4.3)	1 (1.4)				
	More	2 (2.9)	0 (0.0)				
Request for veterinary services	Yes	64 (91.4)	49 (70.0)	10.324	1	0.001	Significant (P<0.01)
	No	6 (8.6)	21 (30.0)				

* Figures in parenthesis are percentages.

Table 3b: Chi-squares test of small ruminant production characteristics in NAERLS-adopted and Non-adopted villages

Variables	Groupings	Adopted villages* (NAV)	Non-adopted villages* (NADV)	Chi-squares	Degree of freedom	Probability level	Decision
Use of improved practices	Yes	37 (52.9)	16 (22.9)	13.390	1	0.000	Significant (P<0.05)
	No	33 (47.1)	54 (77.1)				
Source of finance	Personal	59 (84.3)	58 (82.9)	7.479	2	0.024	Significant (P<0.05)
	Borrowed	11 (15.7)	6 (8.6)				
	Both	0 (0.0)	6 (8.6)				
Membership of farmers association	Yes	68 (97.1)	12 (17.1)	91.467	1	0.000	Significant (P<0.05)
	No	2 (2.9)	58 (82.9)				
Access to extension services	Yes	64 (91.4)	20 (28.6)	57.895	1	0.000	Significant (P<0.01)
	No	6 (8.6)	49 (71.4)				
Type of products usually obtained	Meat	40 (57.1)	46 (65.7)	3.752	3	0.290	Not significant (P>0.05)
	Milk	2 (2.9)	1 (1.4)				
	Meat and skin	16 (22.9)	8 (11.4)				
	All the products	12 (17.1)	15 (21.4)				
In which type of market you sell your animals	Organized	7 (10.0)	11 (15.7)	5.359	2	0.069	Not significant (P>0.05)
	Un-organized	11 (15.7)	20 (28.6)				
	Both	52 (74.3)	39 (55.7)				
Is sheep and goats rearing profitable	Yes	70 (100.0)	57 (81.4)	14.331	2	0.001	Significant (P<0.01)
	No	0 (0.0)	10 (7.1)				
	I don't know	0 (0.0)	3 (4.3)				

* Figures in parenthesis are percentages.

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